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Assessing the Impact of Constituency Projects on Sustainable Development in Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

This study examined the effect of constituency projects on sustainable development in Nasarawa State, Nigeria, concentrating on four critical sectors: education, healthcare, potable water, and electricity. Specifically, the study explored the nature and sources of constituency projects in the state, evaluated their alignment with sustainability objectives and sector-specific impacts, and identified the challenges and constraints affecting their implementation. The analysis was anchored on Political Representation Theory as its guiding theoretical framework. Adopting a descriptive research design, the study utilized a mixed-methods approach that integrated quantitative and qualitative techniques, drawing on both primary and secondary data sources. The study population comprised 1,124,882 residents across six Local Government Areas selected from the three senatorial districts of Nasarawa State, from which a sample size of 386 respondents was drawn. Data were analyzed using descriptive statistics such as simple percentages, alongside inferential tools, including the chi-square test, to examine relationships among variables and strengthen the validity of the findings. The results indicated a statistically significant positive relationship between constituency projects and sustainable development, particularly within the sectors investigated, highlighting the critical role of sustained infrastructural investment in rural communities. Nonetheless, the study identified key challenges, including irregular funding, inadequate monitoring mechanisms, and limited community participation. Consequently, the study recommends improved alignment of constituency projects with the Sustainable Development Goals through the adoption of sustainable infrastructure practices and comprehensive environmental, social, and economic impact assessments. It further advocates for strengthened monitoring systems, increased community engagement, consistent funding, and enhanced maintenance strategies to ensure long-term developmental outcomes.

Keywords: Constituency Projects, Sustainable Development and Mixed-Methods Approach

INTRODUCTION

Across the globe, constituency-based development initiatives play a vital role in advancing sustainable development and alleviating poverty, particularly in rural and underserved communities. The United Nations Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) emphasize the need to improve living conditions through sustainable infrastructure, enhanced agricultural practices, and expanded economic opportunities,

especially in rural areas (United Nations, 2015). Similarly, global development efforts focus on addressing persistent challenges such as poor infrastructure, limited access to basic social services, and economic marginalization that hinder rural development (World Bank, 2020).

Sustainable development strategies worldwide commonly prioritize investments in infrastructure, education, healthcare, and local economic activities. International development institutions, notably the World Bank, support projects aimed at strengthening local economies and improving living standards through stakeholder participation and inclusive development frameworks (World Bank, 2021). These initiatives are intended not only to raise the quality of life in rural communities but also to reduce disparities between rural and urban areas.

In Africa, sustainable development remains a major policy priority due to the high proportion of the population residing in rural areas and the persistent challenges of poverty, weak infrastructure, and inadequate access to essential services (African Development Bank, 2020). The African Union's Agenda 2063 articulates a vision of inclusive growth and sustainable development, emphasizing community-based initiatives and equitable resource distribution as pathways to achieving "The Africa We Want" (African Union, 2015). Consequently, many African countries have implemented development programmes focusing on infrastructure provision, agricultural support, and community empowerment to promote long-term growth (UNICEF, 2021).

In Nigeria, the roots of organized sustainable and rural development efforts can be traced back to the colonial era of the 1920s, when community development was adopted as a strategy for developing rural areas (Ahmed et al., 2015). By the late 1950s, the colonial administration introduced agricultural development schemes such as the Farmers Settlement Scheme (1959–1960), aimed at encouraging youth participation in farming, improving livelihoods, and reducing rural–urban migration (Ahmed et al., 2018). These initiatives sought to establish farming as a viable career path and stabilize rural populations.

Following independence in 1960, successive Nigerian governments intensified efforts to promote sustainable and rural development through a series of national policies and intervention programmes implemented at the federal, state, and local government levels. Notable among these were the First to Fourth National Development Plans, the River Basin Development Authorities (1976), Operation Feed the Nation, the Green Revolution Programme, the Directorate of Food, Roads and Rural Infrastructure (DFRRI), the Better Life Programme for Rural Women, and the National Economic Empowerment and Development Strategy (NEEDS), among others. These programmes were designed to address infrastructural deficits, boost agricultural productivity, and improve living conditions in rural areas.

The continued emphasis on sustainable development reflects government concern over persistent rural–urban migration and uneven development, particularly given that over 60 percent of Nigeria's population resides in rural areas (World Bank, 2023). Over time, development approaches have evolved toward participatory and decentralized models, recognizing that local involvement in planning and implementation enhances project sustainability and effectiveness (Smith & Jenkins, 2018).

Within this context, constituency projects have emerged as a global development mechanism, particularly in democratic systems. Known as "pork barrel" projects in the United States, similar schemes operate in countries such as India, Kenya, Ghana, Malaysia, and several African nations (Awofeso & Irabor, 2022). Studies indicate that legislators often prioritize constituency services due to their direct impact on voters' welfare (Oyeabor, 2022; Ibanga, 2021). While these projects have contributed to improvements in infrastructure and service delivery, they have also generated debates concerning transparency, equity, and effectiveness.

In Nigeria, constituency projects were introduced to channel development initiatives in sectors such as education, healthcare, water supply, electricity, and rural infrastructure directly to grassroots communities (Ibrahim & Ahmad, 2021). These projects are intended to complement state and local government efforts and ensure equitable development across constituencies, including those in Nasarawa State.

Despite their objectives, the impact of constituency projects on sustainable development remains contested. In Nasarawa State, significant disparities persist between urban centers and rural communities, with many areas lacking basic infrastructure and essential services (Adeolu & Ebohon, 2020). Constituency projects aim to address these challenges by investing in key development sectors, thereby

improving service delivery and quality of life. However, the extent to which these projects have achieved their intended goals requires systematic evaluation.

Given the strategic importance of sustainable development at the global, continental, and national levels, a comprehensive assessment of the effects of constituency projects on sustainable development in Nasarawa State is imperative. Such an assessment will provide evidence-based insights to inform policy formulation and implementation, not only in Nigeria but also in other developing countries with similar governance structures.

Literature Review and Theoretical Framework

Conceptual Review

Constituency Projects

According to Awor and Ojobo (2024), constituency projects in Nigeria are development-oriented initiatives sponsored by members of the National and State Assemblies to address infrastructural and socio-economic deficiencies within their constituencies, using public funds. These initiatives focus on providing essential infrastructure such as schools, healthcare facilities, roads, and water supply systems across both rural and urban communities. Funding for constituency projects is drawn mainly from the national budget, with each legislator allocated a defined amount annually to implement projects within their respective constituencies (National Assembly, 2023). Similarly, the World Bank (2012) describes constituency projects as government-driven development interventions that encourage active participation of local communities in decisions concerning the selection, funding, and execution of development projects at the grassroots level. These projects are designed to reflect the specific needs and priorities of individual constituencies. The underlying rationale for constituency projects is to decentralize development efforts and ensure equitable distribution of public resources across Nigeria's diverse regions. However, their execution has attracted significant criticism, particularly regarding issues of transparency, accountability, and political interference (Okoli, 2019). Despite their intended objectives, scholars argue that constituency projects often encounter challenges such as delayed implementation, mismanagement of funds, and weak monitoring mechanisms (Olowu, 2020). In contrast, proponents maintain that constituency projects enhance democratic governance by enabling legislators to respond directly to the needs of their constituents, foster grassroots development, and strengthen representative democracy (Omotola, 2012). Despite the controversies surrounding their implementation, constituency projects continue to play a prominent role in Nigeria's governance framework, shaping rural development outcomes and influencing the socio-economic conditions of communities nationwide.

Onuoha (2018) further characterizes constituency projects as government-funded development initiatives executed within legislative constituencies, with funds allocated to lawmakers who nominate projects and oversee their implementation in line with community demands. While the terminology used to describe constituency projects varies across countries in Africa and beyond, their fundamental purpose remains consistent: to serve as a mechanism through which elected representatives facilitate the provision of government infrastructure and development benefits to their constituencies. Udefuna (2013) defines constituency projects as federally funded initiatives implemented on behalf of members of the National Assembly, while Orimogunje (2015) views them as projects conceived, designed, or executed within a legislative constituency through the influence or involvement of the elected legislator, and financed through either the national or state budget. Similarly, BudgIT Tracka (2018) describes constituency projects as public initiatives nominated by federal legislators to deliver democratic dividends to their constituencies. However, this definition has been criticized for its narrow focus on National Assembly projects, as constituency projects also operate within State Houses of Assembly in Nigeria. From a policy perspective, constituency projects represent legislative development interventions aimed at enhancing effective representation by delivering tangible development benefits to constituents. Yusuf (2018) defines them as projects executed by the federal or state government in return for legislative support on critical policy matters. This perspective suggests that constituency projects may function as inducements by the executive arm to secure legislative backing, potentially undermining the constitutional principle of checks and balances. Building on this argument, Orimogunje (2015) contends that constituency projects amount to an encroachment on executive responsibilities and constitute a violation of constitutional provisions

and the doctrine of separation of powers. Supporting this view, Oni (2013) explains that effective governance requires a clear division of governmental powers among institutions, with each performing distinct functions toward achieving state objectives. Oni (2013) further observes that constitutional systems universally recognize three core arms of government: the legislature, executive, and judiciary. In the same vein, Awor (2020) traces the doctrine of separation of powers to Aristotle, noting that legislative bodies are responsible for lawmaking, the executive for policy implementation, and the judiciary for dispute resolution. Oyediran (2013) similarly emphasizes that in modern states, governmental authority is distributed among distinct institutions responsible for lawmaking, policy execution, and adjudication. Collectively, these perspectives suggest that while the legislature should not directly execute development projects, there is no inherent constitutional violation in lawmakers initiating development intervention policies for executive implementation, particularly when such policies are designed to promote rural and constituency-level development.

Sustainable Development

Sustainable development is a widely discussed and multidimensional concept that has gained prominence in global development discourse due to increasing concerns about environmental degradation, economic inequality, and social injustice. At its core, sustainable development seeks to balance present development needs without compromising the ability of future generations to meet their own needs (World Commission on Environment and Development [WCED], 1987). This definition, articulated in the Brundtland Report, remains the most authoritative and frequently cited conceptualization of sustainable development. Conceptually, sustainable development integrates three interdependent dimensions: economic growth, social inclusion, and environmental protection. These dimensions are often referred to as the “triple bottom line” of sustainability (Elkington, 1997). Economic sustainability emphasizes long-term economic growth, productivity, and efficient resource use. Social sustainability focuses on equity, social justice, poverty reduction, access to education and healthcare, and improved quality of life. Environmental sustainability underscores the protection of ecosystems, conservation of natural resources, and mitigation of climate change and environmental degradation (Mensah, 2019). The economic dimension of sustainable development advocates growth that is inclusive, resilient, and capable of generating employment and income without excessive depletion of natural resources (Todaro & Smith, 2020). It stresses the need for productive economic activities that enhance living standards while maintaining macroeconomic stability. However, economic growth alone is insufficient if it exacerbates inequality or undermines environmental integrity, thereby necessitating integration with social and environmental objectives.

Social sustainability emphasizes human development, equity, and participation. It seeks to address issues such as poverty, unemployment, gender inequality, and social exclusion while promoting access to basic services, including education, healthcare, water, and sanitation (United Nations Development Programme [UNDP], 2020). Participation of local communities and stakeholders is a central element of social sustainability, as inclusive decision-making enhances ownership, accountability, and long-term development outcomes (Sen, 1999). Environmental sustainability focuses on maintaining ecological balance and safeguarding natural resources for future generations. It involves responsible management of land, water, forests, and energy resources, as well as reducing pollution and greenhouse gas emissions (United Nations Environment Programme [UNEP], 2019). Environmental sustainability recognizes that unchecked exploitation of natural resources threatens biodiversity, food security, and human survival, making environmental protection a fundamental pillar of development. At the global level, sustainable development gained renewed momentum with the adoption of the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) in 2015. The SDGs provide a comprehensive framework comprising 17 interconnected goals aimed at eradicating poverty, reducing inequality, promoting inclusive economic growth, and protecting the environment by 2030 (United Nations, 2015). The SDGs emphasize the universality of sustainable development, recognizing that both developed and developing countries share responsibility for achieving sustainability. In developing countries, particularly in Africa, sustainable development is closely linked to addressing structural challenges such as poverty, inadequate infrastructure, weak institutions, and environmental vulnerability (African Development Bank, 2020).

Sustainable development strategies in these contexts often prioritize rural development, agricultural productivity, infrastructure provision, and community empowerment as pathways to inclusive growth and poverty reduction (World Bank, 2021). Decentralized and participatory approaches are increasingly emphasized, as they enhance responsiveness to local needs and improve development effectiveness. Despite its broad acceptance, sustainable development has been criticized for its conceptual ambiguity and implementation challenges. Some scholars argue that the concept is too broad and normatively loaded, making it difficult to translate into concrete policies and measurable outcomes (Hopwood, Mellor, & O'Brien, 2005). Others contend that tensions often arise between economic growth and environmental protection, particularly in resource-dependent economies (Daly, 1996). These critiques highlight the need for context-specific strategies, strong institutions, and effective governance mechanisms to achieve sustainable development goals.

In summary, sustainable development represents a holistic approach to development that seeks to harmonize economic progress, social well-being, and environmental protection. While its implementation remains complex and context-dependent, the concept provides a vital framework for addressing contemporary global and local development challenges. Achieving sustainable development requires coordinated efforts among governments, private sector actors, civil society, and local communities to ensure that development is inclusive, equitable, and environmentally responsible.

Theoretical Framework

This study looked at many theories that relate to the study, such as Principal-Agent theory, Accountability theory, Big Push theory and Political Representation theory but adopted the political representation theory for anchoring the study.

Principal- Agent Theory

Principal-agent theory was postulated by Stephen Ross Rees in 1985. The theory is of the view that there is a relationship between the principal and agents. The agents exercised authority on behalf of the principal. The agents carry out duties and responsibilities that would yield positive results as dividends to the principals, who are shareholders, like in the case of an organization (Oliva and Nyangau; 2022). Further, the theory holds that the principals, in hiring an agent, need to take into consideration two main factors that may hinder task performance and service delivery by the agents.

Oliva and Nyangau (2022) furthermore, argued that it is important to select the best agents and create a conducive atmosphere for the agents to work and perform in accordance with the wishes of their principal. Hence, the principal has to closely watch the behaviours of the agents in order to ensure that their performances, when measured, score them above board or within the range of acceptance by the principals in all ramifications. (Ayee, 2018), cited in (Oliva and Nyangau, 2022).

The relevance of the principal agent theory is predicated on the fact that the legislators, who are representatives, are the agents, while the people (the electorates) are the principals, and as such, they are bound to act as such (agents). In performing their duties as legislators, who are representatives of the citizens who are their principals and who elected them to represent them at the National Assembly as agents, they are expected to work towards the delivery of democracy dividends to their principals, who are electorates in their various constituencies across the country. It is in light of this that legislators, being agents that work towards the satisfaction of their principals (the citizens), deemed it fit and appropriate for the policy of constituency projects to their constituencies to enhance rural development at the grassroots, thereby yielding the dividends of democracy as it is usually referred to for the electorates at their constituencies to justify effective representation.

The criticism of the application of this theory has been that the representatives acting as agents could be motivated to act on their own peculiar interests rather than those of their principals, and moreover, the agents (representatives) worked with the unelected bureaucrats whose actions are accounted for by the voters rather than for themselves and their own interests, which may hinder the success of the representatives as agents in delivering the adequacy of their principals.

Empirical Review

Achibong (2021), in his study on National Assembly constituency projects in Uyo, Akwa-Ibom State presented the main objective of the study being to assess the effect of National Assembly constituency projects on educational infrastructure development. The study utilized a mixed-methods approach and the findings highlighted their positive effect on educational infrastructure, such as the construction and renovation of schools, and the study revealed challenges, including delays and mismanagement, which hinder project outcomes. However, the research is limited by its focus on Uyo, restricting generalizability. The study also lacks an in-depth exploration of the causes of delays and mismanagement, and does not address the long-term sustainability or community involvement in these projects. The study offers useful insights but could benefit from a broader scope, clearer policy recommendations, and a stronger theoretical framework for understanding the effectiveness of such projects in educational infrastructure development.

Yusuf and Ahmed (2020) conducted a quantitative analysis to evaluate the effect of National Assembly constituency projects on educational infrastructure in Kuje Area Council, FCT, Abuja. The study aimed to assess the changes in educational infrastructure before and after project implementation, using primary and secondary data. The findings revealed improvements in the quantity of infrastructure, with a noticeable increase in the number of schools and facilities. However, concerns about the quality of the infrastructure remained, as some projects did not meet expected standards. The study recommended enhanced monitoring and evaluation of constituency projects to ensure adherence to quality standards and ensure the durability of the infrastructure. This highlights the importance of quality control in public projects to achieve long-term benefits. The study lacks qualitative insights into quality issues and broader comparisons with other regions, limiting its generalizability. It also could benefit from more detailed data. Sani and Ahmed (2019) focus on infrastructure improvements is crucial, but the study could have expanded to address systemic challenges like funding inconsistencies and policy gaps that contribute to the uneven distribution of projects. More emphasis on the long-term sustainability of these infrastructure projects, particularly in terms of maintenance and resource allocation, would enhance the conclusions. The recommendation for sustained investment and community involvement in ensuring the sustainability of education projects aligns with Adamu and Ibrahim (2018), which calls for continuous support for teacher training, and Ibrahim and Mohammed (2019), which emphasizes community engagement for sustainable outcomes.

Aliyu and Hassan (2018) explored the role of constituency projects in enhancing rural education access, focusing on Kuje Area Council in Abuja. The aim of the study was to examine the implementation processes, outcomes, and challenges of education-related constituency projects. The study applied survey research design and qualitative method. The study revealed that constituency projects have contributed to school construction and provision of learning materials, leading to significant improvements in enrollment rates and educational outcomes. However, challenges such as teacher shortages and socioeconomic disparities were also identified.

Adamu and Ibrahim (2018) examined the impact of constituency projects on teacher training and capacity building in Bwari Area Council, Abuja. The objective of the study was to assess the effectiveness of constituency projects aimed at enhancing teacher quality and professional development. The study utilised a mixed methods approach. The study found that constituency projects targeting teacher training, workshops, and educational resources improved teaching practices and student learning outcomes. However, challenges such as limited funding and sustainability issues were identified. The study concluded that teacher shortages, and socioeconomic disparities posed challenges to equitable access and quality education. The study recommended for holistic approach to address both supply-side and demand-side factors to achieve universal education access and enhance learning outcomes in rural areas.

Salisu and Rozita (2016) examined the role of education in rural development, focusing on key areas such as poverty, health, gender, agriculture, and democracy. The study found that education positively impacts rural development, particularly in creating employment opportunities across societies. It highlighted education's multidimensional influence on national, economic, political, cultural, and technological aspects of rural areas. The study concluded that education plays a crucial role in the development process,

emphasizing its potential to transform rural communities by addressing various socio-economic challenges.

Ibrahim and Mohammed (2019) study highlighted the importance of community engagement but could benefit from a more detailed examination of the specific mechanisms through which community involvement leads to sustainable outcomes. A discussion on how to address power dynamics and resource constraints would further enrich the study. This study’s findings align with Okeke and Nwachukwu (2018) and Ibrahim (2017), both of which emphasised the role of community involvement in ensuring the sustainability of constituency projects. The emphasis on building inclusive partnerships also resonates with Sani and Ahmed (2019), who highlighted the need for community involvement in sustaining educational infrastructure.

Research Gap

Existing empirical studies show that National Assembly constituency projects have positively contributed to educational development in Nigeria through school construction, renovation, teacher training, and increased enrolment. However, these studies are largely limited to specific urban or peri-urban areas, which restricts the generalizability of their findings to predominantly rural states such as Nasarawa. Additionally, most studies emphasize short-term outputs rather than the long-term sustainability of educational infrastructure, with limited exploration of institutional factors such as maintenance, funding continuity, monitoring, and policy coordination. Although community participation is acknowledged as important, there is insufficient analysis of how community involvement practically influences project sustainability and effectiveness. Furthermore, existing research often examines isolated aspects of education without integrating infrastructure, teacher availability, socio-economic conditions, and policy implementation within a holistic framework. The literature also lacks strong theoretical grounding and comparative analyses across regions. These gaps underscore the need for a comprehensive, context-specific study that evaluates the sustainability, community participation, and institutional effectiveness of constituency projects in advancing educational development in Nigeria.

METHODOLOGY

Study Area

Location of the Study

Nasarawa state is located in the North-Central region of Nigeria, bordering the Federal Capital Territory (FCT) to the west, Kaduna state to the north, Plateau state to the east, and Kogi and Benue states to the south. Nasarawa state, which was created on October 1, 1996, from the old Plateau state covers an area of approximately 26,256 square kilometers (National Population Commission, 2006 Census).. The state has had several governors since its creation, with the current governor being Governor Abdullahi Sule.

Nasarawa State has a projected population of about 3,182,489 people. With the 2006 population standing at 1,869,377 people based on the 2006 census. The current projected population was reached using the exponential growth model, growing to 3,182,489 by 2024 as follows:

Base population in 2006:1,869,377

Annual growth rate: 3.0% (used by the National Population Commission in its state projections)

We apply the formula for exponential growth rate

$$P_t = P_0(1+r)^t$$

Where:

P_0 = the projected population (2024 figure)

P_1 = the base year population (2026 figure)

r = the population growth rate at 3.0% (NPC, 2016)

n = the number of years/interval (18 years)

Therefore:

$$P_0 = 1,869,377$$

$$r = 0.03$$

$$t = 2024 - 2006 = 18 \text{ years}$$

so:

$$\begin{aligned} P_{2024} &= 1,869,377 \times (1 + 0.03)^{18} \\ &= 1,869,377 \times (1.03)^{18} \\ &= 3,182,489 \end{aligned}$$

The state is inhabited by various ethnic groups, including the Eggon, Alago, Mada and Keffi. The capital of Nasarawa State is Lafia. The state is divided into 13 Local Government Areas: Akwanga, Awe, Doma, Garaku, Keana, Keffi, Kokona, Lafia, Nasarawa, Nasarawa Eggon, Obi and Wamba.

Nasarawa State is rich in mineral resources, including limestone, marble, salt and coal. The state's economy is primarily driven by agriculture, with crops like yams, cassava, and maize being major staples. Other economic activities include mining, livestock production and trade.

Nasarawa State has several institutions of higher learning, including the Nasarawa State University, Keffi, Federal University, Lafia, and College of Agriculture Lafia. The state also has several hospitals and healthcare centers, including the Dalhatu Araf specialist hospital lafia. Nasarawa State has a rich cultural heritage, with various ethnic groups contributing to its diverse cultural landscape. Tourist attractions in the state include the Farin Ruwa Waterfalls, the Eggon Hills and the Lafia museum.

Research design

Research design is broadly referred to as the steps taken in carrying out research. (Kathari, 2014). The survey design deals with the creation of decisions regarding the techniques that are utilized in gathering data, the type of strategies and instrument for sampling and ways used for conducting this study through the use of structural questionnaires, in-depth interviews, adapted and modified, as well as observations. Assessing the impact of constituency projects on sustainable development in Nasarawa State is descriptive in nature because the variables involved in the research have to be thoroughly described in order to provide a linkage that would eventually provide answers to what the study objectives seek in the field. Since mixed method survey design is used to collect large and standardized data from the field by a researcher from a sample study. However, the adoption of qualitative and quantitative data methods through survey design is based on the fact that, since each method has its weaknesses, the use of both qualitative and quantitative methods neutralizes the weaknesses of the other. Application of the qualitative method is also predicated by the fact that the attributes of the relationship between constituency projects and sustainable community development are a conscious and concise approach that could be adequately captured using a descriptive survey research design. Further, a qualitative approach enables the researcher to carry out a proper appraisal of the process that leads to the evaluation of data generated from secondary sources, while a quantitative approach engages in the systematic empirical investigation of quantitative properties as well as phenomena using survey design in data collection and statistical techniques in data analysis (Oni, 2013). Furthermore, in support of the combination of quantitative and qualitative methods in survey design, Kathari (2011) observed that these two methods of data generation in research are usually complementary and could reflect on a research design. Finally, this study is descriptive in nature, as stated above. The adoption of the design is supported by Otti (2015), who noted that a descriptive approach to research is able to closely assess a specific situation and present its results the way they are, thereby exposing the elements and attributes of any phenomenon.

Reconnaissance Survey

The focus areas for this study are six (6) Local Government Areas (LGAs), selected across the three senatorial zones of Nasarawa State: Nasarawa South comprising Awe LGA and Keana LGA, Nasarawa North comprising Wamba LGA and Akwanga LGA and Nasarawa West comprising Keffi LGA and Nasarawa LGA. According to the National Population Commission (2006 Census).

The reconnaissance survey was conducted through field visits to each of the selected LGAs, brief interviews with local residents and community leaders, observation of physical infrastructure and other constituency projects, informal discussions with local government officials and use of local guides for orientation and community mapping.

During the survey, it was observed that most LGAs have a variety of constituency projects, including boreholes, classroom blocks, health centres, access roads and culverts and electricity projects. Some projects appeared abandoned or incomplete but the study focused on completed projects.

All areas were accessible though rainy season conditions impacted some road travel in Wamba and Awe. There were also no major security concerns were observed, though Keana and Awe had areas with seasonal tension due to farmer-herder issues, none of these impacted the study.

However, a few challenges were encountered during the survey such as incomplete or lack of signage on some projects which made identification difficult, limited or no documentation at the LGA level on constituency project records and language barriers in rural communities requiring local interpreters. As a result, the researcher resolved to use local guides and interpreters to aid communication and navigation, ensure early notification and formal letters to community leaders and LGA offices and plan travel routes carefully, especially in hard-to-reach areas.

The reconnaissance survey provided valuable insight into the nature and distribution of constituency projects across the selected LGAs. The study areas were feasible for study with proper logistical planning and stakeholder engagement in order to inform the design and execution of the main study aimed at assessing the real impact of these projects on the residents of Nasarawa State.

Sources of Data

Both primary and secondary data sources were used for the study. Primary data were collected through well-structured questionnaires and oral in-depth interviews. The questionnaire contained closed ended questions using the Likert Scale. (With the range of 1-5) and divided into four sections, each section addressed a specific segment of the research question. Section A of the questionnaire sought demographic information on the personal background of the respondents such as age, sex, educational level, marital status, LGA. While other sections addressed the research objectives by providing the answers to the research questions raised in the study. The secondary data were sourced from Journals, Budget Reports, print and electronic media publications, legislative documents on constituency projects in the Appropriation Acts as well as Reports of Legislative Committees Oversight of Zonal Intervention Projects (ZIPs) as well as from the Fiscal Responsibility Commission’s reports of Physical verification of FGN capital projects.

Population and Sample Size

The population comprised of residents of two (2) LGAs each from the three (3) Senatorial zones of Nasarawa State. The LGAs comprises of Awe LGA, and Keana LGA; (Nasarawa South) Wamba LGA and Akwanga LGA; (Nasarawa North) Keffi LGA and Nasarawa LGA (Nasarawa West) with total population of 660,650 as of 2006.

According to the National Population Commission (NPC), 2006 census in Nigeria, and projected figure for 2024 using growth rate at 3.0%, the total population of the six (6) local government areas is tabulated below.

Table 3.2.1 Population of Representative LGAs of Nasarawa State

S/N	LGA	Population (2006 census)	Projected Population (2024)
1.	Awe	112,574	191,650
2.	Keana	79,253	134,923
3.	Wamba	72,894	124,267
4.	Akwanga	113,430	193,107
5	Keffi	92,664	157,754
6	Nasarawa	189,835	323,181
TOTAL	6	660,750	1,124,882

Source: National population commission (2006, 2016)

Sample Size: The sample size for this study is drawn from six LGAs, two (2) representing one Senatorial zone. The total study population of these six (6) LGAs is 1,124,882. Taro Yamane (1967) sample size determination formula was applied to determine the sample size for the study from the population above given as;

$$n = \frac{N}{1+N(e)^2}$$

Where n = sample size

N = population size

l constant

e = the assume error margin or tolerable error which is specified as 5% (0.05) in this study.

$$n = \frac{N}{1 + N(e)^2} = \frac{1,124,882}{1 + 1,124,882(0.05)^2} = \frac{1,124,882}{1 + 1,124,882 * 0.0025} = \frac{1,124,882}{2,813.205} = 399.86$$

n=400

N=Sample Size is = 400

Sampling Technique

The primary data obtained from the study (questionnaires) were analyzed using descriptive statistical technique for data analysis. The percentages were presented in frequency distribution tables with the aid of Statistical Package for Social Science Software (SPSS), while qualitative data obtained from the interviews were organized using coding and themes and content analysis to make objective and systematic inferences from the interview data. Every response obtained was examined thematically in consonance with the objective of the study.

Data Collection Instruments

The instruments used in this study have been subjected to a pilot-test to determine their reliability. The pilot study provided the researcher with the opportunity to assess the appropriateness and correctness of the instruments and other procedures in data collection so as to make all the required adjustments if necessary (Ary et al., 2018) and also to ensure the validity and reliability of the research instruments (Saunders, Lewis,&Thornhill, 2021). The pilot test was conducted from January 2025 to March 2025 and was administered to 400 community members. Cronbach's alpha was used in checking for the internal consistency of the instruments. The internal consistency determines if all the items in the instruments are measuring the same thing.

Validity

Validity refers to an agreement between the measurement, and what it is supposed to measure and the quality it is believed to have (Kaplan, Ogut, Kaplan,&Aksay, 2022). Validity demands that a study be accurate because, if the validity of an instrument is not clear, it will be difficult for the researcher to interpret the data correctly (Hair, Black, Babin, Anderson,&Tatham, 2020). Validity is thus the most imperative quality of an instrument which researchers ought to observe carefully (Gay, Mills,&Airasian, 2021). In this study, both the content and construct validity of the questionnaire were examined.

A good research study relies upon the instruments' reliability as well as its validity. According to Franzen and Pointner, (2023), the validity and reliability of a research instrument reflect the correctness of measurement. However, some modifications were done to some in order to reflect the content of the current study. In order to ensure the content validity, all items adapted from previous literature passed through peer review. This justifies the instrument's content validity to measure the construct (Waltz, Candy, Hinton, Estrada-Mila,&Kinsey, 2025) and was considered acceptable and appropriate for the targeted respondents.

Reliability

Reliability in quantitative research has been defined as the degree of consistency with which it measures what it is supposed to measure (Ary et al., 2018) and the reliability of a test indicates whether it is free from bias or not (Sekaran&Bougie, 2016). Therefore, in this study, the researcher used Cronbach's Alpha in testing the reliability of the instrument for the study. It is regarded as a well-known method for testing the reliability of an instrument in a research and is considered perfectly adequate in consistency (Sekaran&Bougie, 2016). Most researchers apply this method in their studies (Peterson, 2019). The Cronbach's Alpha scores were obtained and analyzed using IBM SPSS software version 21.

Data Analysis Methods

The primary data obtained from the study (questionnaires) were analyzed using descriptive statistical technique for data analysis. The percentages were presented in frequency distribution tables with the aid of Statistical Package for Social Science Software (SPSS), while qualitative data obtained from the interviews

were organized using coding and themes and content analysis to make objective and systematic inferences from the interview data. Every response obtained was examined thematically in consonance with the objectives of the study.

To effectively analyze the data collected for easy management and accuracy, the chi-square method was used to test independence. The Chi-square is given as

$$X^2 = \frac{\sum (o-e)^2}{e}$$

Where X^2 = chi-square
 o = observed frequency
 e = expected frequency

Level of confidence/degree of freedom

When employing the chi-square test, a certain level of confidence or margin of error has to be assumed. Moreover, the degree of freedom in the table must be determined in a simple variable, row, and column distribution; the degree of freedom is:

$$df = (r-1) (c-1)$$

Where df = degree of freedom

r = number of rows

c = number of columns.

In determining the critical chi _ square value, the confidence value is assumed to be at 95% or 0.95. A margin of 5% or 0.05 is allowed for judgment error.

Ethical Considerations

Several ethical considerations were undertaken while conducting this study. Consent was obtained, ensuring that all participants, including government officials, community leaders and beneficiaries of constituency projects, provided informed consent before data was collected. There was guarantee of anonymity and confidentiality to participants. Act of objectivity was maintained and the study tried every means to avoid act of bias. The researcher was able to disclose every potential conflict of interest that may affect the reliability and validity of data. The study ensured data accuracy. The study verified the accuracy and reliability of data collected from various sources, including government records, surveys, and interviews.

RESULTS AND DATA ANALYSIS

Data Presentation, Analysis and Discussion of Findings

This section presented, interpreted and discussed the results gathered from questionnaires and interview responses from the research. The researcher’s presentation, analysis and discussion of data were guided by the objectives of the study as outlined in chapter one. Therefore, the data collected is presented, analysed and the findings, discussed. It should be noted that 400 questionnaires were distributed, but 386 were returned representing 96.5%.

Table 4.1 Questionnaire Distribution

Questionnaire	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Returned	386	96.5
Not returned	14	3.5
Total	400	100

Source: Field Survey, 2025.

Demographic and Socio-Economic Characteristics of Respondents

Respondents Gender

Table 4.3 Respondents Gender

Gender	Frequency	Percent
Male	221	57
Female	165	43
Total	386	100.0

Source: Field Survey, 2025.

Table 4.3 above shows the gender distribution of the respondents used for this study. Of the total number of 386 respondents, 221 representing 57 percent of the population are male and 165 representing 43 percent and are female. This shows that there is male dominance in the communities. There is a need to do more especially in terms of education and empowerment to bridge the disparity between the male and female genders willing to participate in research in the society in order to achieve sustainable development like other developed countries of Europe and America.

Age of Respondents

Table 4.4: Age Range of Respondents

Age range	Frequency	percent
18-25 years	67	17
26-35 years	141	37
36-45 years	99	26
46-60 years	55	14
above 60 years	24	6
Total	386	100

Source: Field Survey, 2025.

Table 4.4 above shows the age grade of the respondents used for this study. Of the total 386 respondents, 67, representing 17 percent of the population, are between 18-25 years old. 141 respondents, which represent 37 percent of the population, are between 26-35 years old. 99 respondents, 26 percent of the population, are between 36-45 years old. 55 respondents, representing 14 percent of the population, are between 46-60 years old and 24 respondents, representing 6 percent are above 60 years. This shows that most of the respondents are youth. This indicates that we have a healthy and optimum population, which, if utilized properly, can lead to growth and development in all sectors.

Educational Background of Respondents

Table 4.5: Educational Background of Respondents

Educational Background	Frequency	Percent
No formal Education	38	10
Primary	69	18
Secondary	97	25
Tertiary	121	31
Others	61	16
Total	386	100.0

Source: Field Survey, 2025.

Table 4.5 above shows the educational background of the respondents used for this study. Out of the total number of 386 respondents, 38 respondents, representing 10 percent have no formal education. 69, representing 18 percent of the population, have primary school certificate, 97, representing 25 percent of the population, have secondary school certificates. 121, representing 31 percent of the population, have a tertiary qualification. 61, representing 16 percent of the population, had another educational qualification. These findings indicate that the respondents are literate enough to understand the questions raised in this research. Therefore, proper enlightenment and awareness campaigns will go a long way in involving the communities in the implementation of constituency projects.

Marital Status of respondents

Table 4.6: Marital Status

Marital Status	Frequency	Percentage
Valid Single	130	34.0
Married	198	51.0
Divorced	19	5.0
Widowed	39	10.0
Total	386	100.0

Source: Field Survey.

Table 4.6 above shows the marital status of the respondents used for this study. 130, which represent 34.0 percent of the population, are single. 198, which represent 51.0 percent of the population, are married. 19, which represent 5.0 percent of the population, are divorced. 39, which represent 10.0 percent of the population, are widowed. The result indicates that most of the respondents were married during this research. This implies that most respondents are responsible according to the popular belief that married people are more responsible than singles.

4.1.4 Number of years lived in Nasarawa State

Table 4.6: Number of years lived in Nasarawa State

Number of years	Frequency	Percent
Less than 5 years	41	11
5-10 years	79	20
11 – 20 years	192	50
More than 20 years	74	19
Total	386	100.0

Source: Field Survey, 2025.

Table 4.6 above shows the number of years respondents have lived in Nasarawa state. Of 386 respondents used for this study. 41 which represents 11 percent of the population, have lived in Nasarawa for less than 5 years. 79, which represents 20 percent of the population, have lived in Nasarawa between 5 to 10 years. 192 which represents 50 percent of the population, have lived between 11-20 years and 74, which represents 19 percent of the population, have been there more than 20 years. The result indicates that most of the respondents have lived in the study area for more than 10 years which is the period covered by this research. This implies that most respondents have been present during the implementation of the constituency projects under review.

Analysis of Data Alignment with Research Objectives

Objective One: To examine the nature and origin of constituency projects in Nasarawa State

In Table 4.7 of Appendix 3, respondents’ views were sought on the influence of political and community priorities on the nature and origin of constituency projects’ implementation and sustainable development of Nasarawa State. Responding, 135 (35%), strongly agreed that there was influence of political and community priorities on the nature and origin of constituency projects in Nasarawa state, while 74 (19%) agreed, indicating a positive view among a substantial number of respondents regarding the nature and origin of constituency projects implementation in their communities. However, 80 (21%) strongly disagreed, 76 (20 %) disagreed. The 21 (5%) undecided suggests some uncertainty in responses by the respondents. Hence, from the responses, the study concluded that political considerations or community needs has an impact on the origin and nature of constituency projects in Nasarawa State.

Interview - Influence of Political and Community priorities on the Nature and origin of Constituency Projects

Code 1: Awareness of Constituency projects in my Community: Most respondents mentioned they were aware of constituency projects going on in their communities. Some did not know that the projects were constituency projects.

Code 2: Participation in constituency projects: Many respondents noted that they participated in various capacities. This suggests a good relationship between the elected officials and the constituents.

Code 3: Determination of constituency projects: Respondents acknowledged the significant role of constituency projects in improving infrastructure and welfare. However, their opinions were not sought before determining the type of projects to be implemented.

Objective Two: To examine the nature and origin of constituency projects in Nasarawa State

In Table 4.8 of Appendix 3, respondents’ views as to whether constituency projects align with sustainable development goals. Responding, 62 respondents, representing (16%) indicated strongly agreed, 178 (46%) respondents indicated agreed that constituency projects align with sustainable development goals a higher percentage of the community had access to potable water now compared to before constituency projects. 15 (4%) were undecided in their responses to the question asked, while 85 (22%) respondents indicated strongly agreed and 46 (12%) indicated disagreed that constituency projects do not align with sustainable development goals.

Alignment with Sustainable Development Principles (Interview)

Code 1: Familiarity with the term Sustainable Development: Most respondents understood what sustainable development meant and what the principles entailed.

Code 2: Impact of completed constituency projects: Many respondents noted that the quality of constituency projects was good but there was no maintenance culture when there were defects.

Objective three: To assess the impact of constituency projects on four key development sectors: education, healthcare, potable water supply and electricity supply in Nasarawa State.

Constituency Projects and Provision of Educational Infrastructure-

In Table 4.9 of Appendix 3 respondents' views were sought on constituency projects' implementation and sustainable development of Nasarawa State. Responding, 142 (37%), strongly agree that educational facilities have improved due to constituency projects, while 73 (19%) agree, indicating a positive view among a substantial number of respondents regarding the improvement of educational facilities as a result of constituency projects implementation in their communities. However, 70 (18%) strongly disagreed, 80 (21 %) disagreed that there is improvement in educational facilities. The 21 (5%) undecided suggests some uncertainty in responses by the respondents. Hence, from the responses, the study concluded that educational facilities in these communities have improved due to constituency projects leading to sustainable development in Nasarawa State.

Table 4.10 in Appendix 3 shows responses as to whether there has been an increase in the number of teachers in schools in my community due to constituency projects. 124 (32%) respondents indicated strongly agreed, 190 (49 %) respondents indicated agreed, 13 (3%) indicated undecided in their responses, while 33 (8%) respondents indicated strongly disagreed and 36 (6%) respondents indicated disagreed that there has been an increase in the number of teachers in schools in my community due to constituency projects.

Table 4.11 of Appendix 3 shows the responses as to whether constituency projects have improved access to educational infrastructure e.g., classrooms, furniture, water, toilets are as follows: 136 (35%) respondents indicated strongly agreed, 117 (30%) respondents indicated agreed, 20 (5%) respondents were undecided, while 50 (13%) respondents indicated strongly disagreed and 63 (16%) disagreed that constituency projects improved access to educational infrastructure such as classrooms, furniture, water, toilets in rural communities.

The responses in Table 4.12 of Appendix 3, as to whether there is increase in number of children enrollment in schools in the communities revealed that a majority of respondents, 76 (20%) indicated strongly agreed, 147 (38%) respondents indicated agreed that constituency projects significantly affected school enrollment. 66 (17%) respondents and 62 (16%) respondents indicated strongly agreed and agreed respectively that the projects had increased children enrollment in schools in the community.

In table 4.13 of Appendix 3, The responses as to whether there is increase in academic performance of children in schools in the LGAs, data on children's academic performance in relation to constituency projects show that 69 (18%) respondents indicated strongly agreed, 135 (35%) respondents indicated agreed, 12 (3%) respondents indicated undecided. While 89 (23%) respondents strongly disagreed, 81 (21%) respondents indicated disagreed that children's academic performance had increased in the LGAs due to constituency projects.

Educational Infrastructure (Interview)

Theme: Improved Quality of Educational Facilities

Code 1: Improved Infrastructure: The respondents highlighted the construction of school buildings, including the provision of desks, classrooms, toilets, and water facilities. These improvements were directly linked to increased school enrollment and the engagement of teachers.

Code 2: Increased Enrollment: Many respondents noted that the improved facilities led to a rise in school enrollment. This suggests a positive relationship between infrastructure improvement and educational participation.

Code 3: Resource Availability: Increased availability of essential resources like desks, chairs, and sanitation facilities were frequently mentioned as a contributing factor to the improvement in education.

Respondents emphasized the significant role of constituency projects in improving educational infrastructure, demonstrating a strong positive effect on educational facilities and access to learning.

Constituency Projects and Provision of Potable Water

In table 4.14 of Appendix 3, Responses as to whether access to potable water sources in my community has increased due to constituency projects. 159 (41%) respondents indicated strongly agreed, 108 (28%) respondents indicated agreed, 42 (11%) respondents indicated undecided to the question asked, while 41 (11%) respondents indicated strongly disagreed and 36 ((9%) respondents disagreed that these projects had not increased access to potable water in the communities.

In Table 4.15 of Appendix 3, the responses as to whether respondents were satisfied with the quality of water provided through constituency projects revealed the following: 132 (34%) respondents indicated strongly agreed, 100 (26%) respondents agreed indicating satisfaction with the quality of water provided and 15 (4%) of the respondents were undecided in response to the question. While 77 (20%) respondents strongly disagreed, 62 (16%) disagreed being satisfied with the quality of water provided through constituency projects.

The responses as to whether constituency projects had reduced the distance to travel to access clean water revealed in Table 4.16 of Appendix 3 that, 112 (29%) respondents indicated strongly agreed, 116 (30%) respondents indicated agreed and 19 (5%) respondents remained undecided in their responses to the question. While 72 (19%) respondents strongly disagreed, 66 (17%) respondents disagreed that constituency projects had not reduced the distance traveled to access clean water in the community.

Responses in Table 4.17 of Appendix 3 as to whether there have been community training programs on water sanitation and hygiene as part of constituency projects, 97 (25%) respondents indicated strongly agreed, 66 (17%) respondents indicated agreed, while 19 (5%) respondents were undecided. 127 (33%) respondents indicated strongly disagreed and 77 (20%) respondents disagreed that there had not been training programs on water sanitation and hygiene due to constituency projects in the community

In Table 4.18 of Appendix 3, respondents views as to whether higher percentage of community now have access to potable water than before the constituency projects, responding, 72 respondents, representing (19%) indicated strongly agreed, 178 (46%) respondents indicated agreed that a higher percentage of the community had access to potable water now compared to before constituency projects, 5 (1%) were undecided in their responses to the question asked, while 85 (22%) respondents indicated strongly agreed and 46 (12%) indicate disagreed that communities do not have more water now than before constituency projects.

Provision of Potable water (Interview)

Theme- Improved Water Accessibility and Quality

Code 1: Reduced Travel Distance: Respondents frequently mentioned a reduction in the distance traveled to fetch water, an important indicator of improvement in water access.

Code 2: Water Quality Improvement: Clean, accessible watersources were identified as a major benefit, alongside the availability of water points that provided safe drinking water.

Code 3: Sanitation and Hygiene Education: Several participants noted the inclusion of sanitation training and hygiene programmes as part of the projects, which were credited to improving community health and water usage habits.

The respondents highlighted these improvements, reflecting significant positive changes in water access, sanitation, and quality of life.

Constituency Projects and Provision of Primary Healthcare Services

Table 4.19 of Appendix 3 showed responses as to whether the quality of primary healthcare services has improved since the implementation of constituency projects. 101 respondents, representing (26%) indicated strongly agreed, 115 (30%) respondents indicated agreed, 50 (13%) were undecided in their responses to the question asked, while 39 (10%) respondents indicated strongly disagree and 81 (21) indicate disagreed that the quality of primary healthcare services has improved since the implementation of constituency projects.

Table 4.20 of Appendix 3 showed responses as to whether constituency projects have led to an increase in healthcare facilities in the community. 108 (28%) respondents indicated strongly agreed, 131 (34%)

respondents indicated agreed, 27 (7%) respondents were undecided in their responses to the question, while 50 (13%) respondents indicated strongly disagreed and 70 (18%) respondents indicated disagreed that constituency projects have led to an increase in healthcare facilities in the community.

In table 4.21 of Appendix 3, responses as to whether healthcare access has improved for women and children in my community due to constituency projects showed that 120 (31%) respondents indicated strongly agreed, 147 (38%) indicated agreed, 15 (4%) respondents were undecided in their responses, while 77 (20%) respondents indicated strongly disagreed and 27 (7%) respondents disagreed that healthcare access has improved for women and children in my community due to constituency projects.

Responses in table 4.22 of Appendix 3 as to whether family members in the community had received healthcare service interventions funded by constituency projects showed that 110 (28%) respondents indicated strongly agreed, 134 (35%) respondents indicated agreed, 39 (10%) respondents were undecided in their responses to the question. While 77 (20%) respondents indicated strongly disagreed, 26 (7%) respondents indicated disagreed that members of the community had received healthcare services intervention funded by constituency projects.

In table 4.23 of Appendix 3 as to whether the availability of healthcare personnel has increased since the introduction of constituency projects, 85 (22%) respondents indicated strongly agreed, 154 (40%) respondents indicated agreed, 27 (7%) respondents were undecided in their responses to the question, while 77 (20%) respondents indicated strongly agreed, and 43 (11%) respondents indicated disagreed that the availability of healthcare personnel has increased since the introduction of constituency projects.

Primary Healthcare Services (Interview)

Theme: Improved Healthcare Facilities and Services

Code 1: *Healthcare Infrastructure:* Many respondents indicated that new or improved healthcare facilities were established in their communities, improving access to medical services, especially for women and children.

Code 2: *Increased Access to Health Services:* Respondents mentioned better access to primary healthcare services, with a specific focus on maternal and child health programs.

Code 3: *Healthcare Interventions:* Constituency projects funded healthcare interventions, which were reported to directly benefit community members through the provision of healthcare services.

Respondents reported positive changes in healthcare access, with a focus on maternal and child healthcare. This reflects the successful effect of constituency projects on rural healthcare delivery.

Constituency Projects and Provision of Electricity

Responses in Table 4.24 of Appendix 3 as to whether household had gained access to electricity due to constituency projects implementation, 116 (30%) respondents indicated strongly agreed, 100 (26%) respondents indicated agreed, 43 (11%) respondents were undecided, while 77 (20%) respondents indicated strongly disagreed and 50 (13%) respondents indicated disagreed that these projects had provided access to electricity to households in the community.

Responses in table 4.25 of Appendix 3 as to whether there is improvement in reliability of electricity supply in the community due to introduction of constituency projects showed that 100 (26%) respondents indicated strongly agreed, 131 (34%) respondents indicated agreed, 40 (10%) respondents were undecided in their responses, while 77 (20%) respondents indicated strongly disagreed, 27 (7%) respondents indicated disagreed that there had not been improvement in the reliability of electricity supply due to constituency projects in the community.

In table 4.26 of Appendix 3, responses as to whether access to electricity has significantly improved my quality of life due to constituency projects showed that 146 (38%) respondents indicated strongly agreed, 74 (19%) respondents indicated agreed, 31 (8%) respondents indicated undecided in their responses, while 85 (22%) respondents indicated strongly disagreed and 50 (13%) indicated disagreed that access to electricity has significantly improved my quality of life due to constituency projects.

In Table 4.27 of Appendix 3, 108 (28%) respondents indicated strongly agreed as to whether there have been community initiatives of solar energy provided by constituency projects., 120 (31%) of respondents indicated agreed, 23 (6%) respondents were undecided in their responses to the question posed to them,

while 50 (13%) respondents indicated strongly disagreed and 85 (22%) respondents indicated disagreed that there have been community initiatives of solar energy provided by constituency projects.

In Table 4.28 of Appendix 3, responses as to whether improved access to electricity due to constituency projects has positively affected local businesses in my community showed that 146 (38%) respondents indicated strongly agreed, 108 (28%) respondents indicated agreed, 31(8%) respondents were undecided in their responses, while 58 (15%) indicated strongly disagreed and 43 (11%) respondents indicated disagreed that improved access to electricity due to constituency projects has positively affected local businesses in my community.

Electricity Access (Interview)

Theme: Increased Access to Electricity and Solar Initiatives

Code 1: Increased Household Electricity Access: Many respondents noted a remarkable improvement in electricity availability, including more reliable power supply to households.

Code 2: Solar Energy Projects: Several participants emphasized the introduction of solar energy as an important development, providing renewable energy options for rural communities.

Code 3: Quality of Life and Economic effect: The improved electricity access positively affected quality of life and local businesses, enabling evening activities and stimulating local economic growth, as shown in both the interview and questionnaire

The respondents identified significant improvements in electricity access, particularly through solar initiatives, which suggests that constituency projects effectively addressed energy needs in rural areas.

Responses shown in Table 4.29 of Appendix 3 as to whether the four key sectors of education, health, water and electricity have improved since the implementation of constituency projects. 100 respondents, representing (26%) indicated strongly agreed, 116 (30%) respondents indicated agreed, 50 (13%) were undecided in their responses to the question asked, while 39 (10%) respondents indicated strongly disagree and 81 (21) indicate disagreed that the four key sectors of education, health, water and electricity have improved since the implementation of constituency projects.

Objective Four: To assess the challenges and limitations associated with the implementation of constituency projects in Nasarawa State.

Responses in Table 4.30 of Appendix 3 as to whether there are challenges in the implementation of constituency projects showed, 146 (38%) respondents indicated strongly agreed, 89 (23%) respondents indicated agreed, 31 (8%) respondents indicated undecided in their responses, while 70 (18%) respondents indicated strongly disagreed and 50 (13%) indicated disagreed that there are challenges in the implementation of constituency projects in Nasarawa State.

Challenges associated with the implementation of Constituency projects in Nasarawa state (Interview)

Code 1: Challenges: Respondents noted a number of challenges associated with the implementation of Constituency projects including lack of awareness and community involvement, inequitable distribution of projects, inadequate monitoring and evaluation, lack of political will.

Code 2: Recommendations for improvement: Several participants emphasized the need for proper community engagement and proper monitoring from authorities as well as equitable distribution of projects. Meanwhile, Table 4.31 of Appendix 4 shows a Constituency Projects Executed by Assembly Members in LGAs of Nasarawa State from 2014 – 2024 for education, health, water and electricity supply.

Test of Hypotheses

Hypothesis One:

Ho: There is no significant influence of political and community priorities on the origin and nature of constituency projects in Nasarawa State.

H1: There is a significant influence of political and community priorities on the origin and nature of constituency projects in Nasarawa State.

Response	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Strongly Agreed	135	%
Agreed	74	%
Undecided	21	%
Disagreed	80	%
Strongly Disagreed	76	%
Total	386	100%

Table 4.31 Testing of Hypothesis (1)

RESPONSE	FO	FE	(FO-FE) ²	(FO-FE) ² /FE
SA	135	77.2	3345.64	43.3
A	74	77.2	10.24	0.13
U	21	77.2	3167	41.0
D	80	77.2	7.84	0.1
SD	76	77.2	1.44	0.02

$$X^2 = 43.3 + 0.13 + 41.0 + 0.1 + 0.02 = 84.55$$

Degrees of freedom (df): No. of categories minus 1

$$df = 5 - 1 = 4$$

Significance level (α): 5% (0.05)

Critical value for df = 4 and SL = 0.05 is 9.488

Decision Rule: Accept the null hypothesis (H_0) if $X^2 < CV$.

Reject the null hypothesis (H_0) if $X^2 > CV$

From the chi-square computation above the Chi-square test result indicates a calculated Chi-square value of 84.55, which is higher than the critical value of 9.488.

Since the calculated value exceeds the critical value, we reject the null hypothesis and accept the alternate hypothesis.

RESULTS

The Chi-square test results, which show a calculated Chi-square value of 84.55, indicate a statistically significant relationship between political considerations and community priorities on the origin and nature of constituency projects in Nasarawa State.

The null hypothesis suggests that there is no significant influence of political considerations and community priorities on the origin and nature of constituency projects in Nasarawa state such as access to educational infrastructure in rural areas, such as classroom blocks, furniture, toilets, and potable water. The alternative hypothesis, on the other hand, asserts that political considerations and community priorities significantly influence the origin and nature of constituency projects in Nasarawa State.

Since the calculated Chi-square value (84.55) exceeds the critical value (9.488) at the 0.05 significance level. This means there is clear statistical evidence that these projects are politically motivated and community priorities are considered.

Discussion of the Findings

The origin of constituency projects in Nasarawa State is rooted in efforts to decentralize development and ensure community-level infrastructure delivery through elected representatives. The findings suggest that these projects emerged as a response to long-standing infrastructural neglect and are typically funded by federal allocations. The nature of these interventions span education, healthcare, water supply, and electricity, emphasizing community-centric priorities. Interview data and document review indicate that

while the projects are often initiated by lawmakers, local community input is limited in many cases. This top-down approach can result in poorly aligned priorities. However, the general consensus is that these projects, when properly executed, have addressed critical infrastructural gaps. The findings imply a need to enhance community participation in the planning and selection phases of constituency projects to align better with actual needs. Clear guidelines and accountability mechanisms should be established to ensure transparency and effectiveness. Constituency projects in Nasarawa State originated as tools for addressing localized development needs but would benefit from greater inclusivity and community ownership in their execution.

Hypothesis Two

Ho: There is no significant alignment between constituency projects in Nasarawa state and sustainable development principles globally.

H1: There is a significant alignment between constituency projects in Nasarawa state and sustainable development principles globally.

Response	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Strongly Agreed	62	16%
Agreed	178	46%
Undecided	15	4%
Disagreed	85	22%
Strongly Disagreed	46	12%
Total	386	100%

Table 4.32 Testing of Hypothesis (2)

RESPONSE	FO	FE	(FO-FE) ²	(FO-FE) ² /E
SA	62	77.2	231.04	43.3
A	178	77.2	101161.6	131.1
U	15	77.2	3873.84	50.2
D	85	77.2	60.84	0.79
SD	46	77.2	973.44	12.6

$X^2 = 43.3 + 131.1 + 50.2 + 0.79 + 12.6 = 197.69$

Degrees of freedom (df): No. of categories minus 1

$df = 5 - 1 = 4$

Significance level (α): 0.05

Critical value for $df = 4$ and $SL = 0.05$ is 9.488

Decision Rule: Since 197.69 (the calculated Chi-square value) is greater than 9.488, we reject the null hypothesis and accept the alternate hypothesis (H_1): Constituency projects in Nasarawa state have significant alignment with sustainable development principles.

Results

The Chi-square test results provide a robust statistical basis to support the findings of this research study on constituency projects in Nasarawa State and its alignment with sustainable development principles globally. The test indicates a significant alignment between the constituency projects in Nasarawa state and sustainable development principles, suggesting that these projects have played crucial roles in bringing sustainable development to Nasarawa State.

Discussion Of The Findings

Statistical analysis using Chi-square tests indicates a strong alignment between constituency projects in Nasarawa State and global sustainable development principles. Projects focused on education, health, electricity, and water supply reflect priorities in the SDGs (particularly SDGs 3, 4, 6, and 7). For example, access to clean water has reduced waterborne diseases and improved sanitation, while electricity access has enabled healthcare equipment functionality and enhanced educational infrastructure all aligning to the economic, social, environmental and political principles of the sustainable development goals. The alignment with sustainable development practices was also confirmed through comparative literature.

Studies by Yusuf&Ahmed (2020) and Okafor&Nwosu (2021) corroborate these findings, suggesting that infrastructure-focused projects in underserved areas can significantly drive rural transformation. This alignment suggests that constituency projects can serve as localized pathways to achieving national and international development commitments. Policymakers and development actors should explore integrating constituency project planning into national SDG implementation strategies. The implementation of constituency projects in Nasarawa State is largely consistent with sustainable development principles, offering significant potential to localize global development goals through community-level interventions.

Hypothesis three

Ho: There is no significant impact of constituency projects on these four key development sectors – education, health care, portable water supply and electricity in Nasarawa state.

H1: There is a significant impact of constituency projects on these four key development sectors – education, health care, portable water supply and electricity in Nasarawa state.

Response	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Strongly Agreed	100	26%
Agreed	116	30%
Undecided	50	13%
Disagreed	39	10%
Strongly Disagreed	81	21%
Total	386	100%

Table 4.33 Testing of Hypothesis (3)

RESPONSE	FO	FE	(FO-FE) ²	(FO-FE) ² /E
SA	100	77.2	519.84	6.73
A	116	77.2	1505.94	19.5
U	50	77.2	739.84	9.57
D	39	77.2	1455.24	18.85
SD	81	77.2	14.44	0.19

$X^2 = 6.73+19.5+9.57+18.85+0.19 =54.84$

Degrees of freedom (df): No. of categories minus 1

$df = 5 - 1 =4$

Significance level (α): 0.05

Critical value for $df = 4$ and significance level = 0.05 is 9.488

Since 54.84 (the calculated Chi-square value) is greater than 9.488, which reject the null hypothesis.

Decision rule: Since the calculated Chi-square value of 54.84 is much greater than the critical value of 9.488, which reject the null hypothesis. This indicates a statistically significant relationship between constituency projects and its impact on education, healthcare, portable water supply and electricity in Nasarawa state.

Since the calculated Chi-square value (54.84) is higher than the critical value (9.488), which reject the null hypothesis. This means that the observed improvements in the quality of the four key sectors – education, healthcare, portable water supply and electricity are not due to random chance, but rather a result of the implementation of constituency projects in Nasarawa State.

The Chi-square test confirms that the implementation of these constituency projects, which focus on infrastructure, has a significant positive impact on sustainable development of communities in Nasarawa State.

Results and findings

The Chi-square result highlighted that constituency projects have made a significant contribution to enhancing the four key development sectors, education, healthcare, portable water supply and electricity

in Nasarawa State. These constituency projects have provided many functional developmental projects which had addressed key infrastructural and supply-related challenges faced by communities in the state. The findings reflect a generally significant effect of constituency projects on the four key development sectors. Communities perceived improvements in these sectors within their communities, with high agreement rates. Similarly, enhanced healthcare access for women and children and access to healthcare interventions for families were also noted, aligning with research highlighting the role of government interventions in healthcare infrastructure improvements.

Discussion Of The Findings

The impact of constituency projects is most evident in the four priority sectors:

Education: The Chi-square test result underscores the importance of continuing and expanding the constituency projects that focus on educational infrastructure. Given the statistical significance of the results, policymakers should consider the findings as strong evidence that investing in educational infrastructure leads to measurable improvements in rural communities. This could inform future policy decisions regarding the allocation of resources and the prioritization of educational development projects, ensuring that the most pressing needs of rural schools are addressed.

Furthermore, the results highlight the need for regular monitoring and evaluation of such constituency projects. The significant effect observed in this study suggests that regular assessments will help ensure that the projects continue to meet the evolving needs of rural schools and improve the overall educational experience for students.

Additionally, the findings suggest that the successful implementation of educational infrastructure projects in rural areas can be a model for addressing other critical needs such as healthcare, water supply, and electricity. A similar approach could be applied to other sectors, ensuring that rural communities across Nasarawa benefit from holistic and sustainable development.

The Chi-square test result, with a calculated value of 84.55 exceeding the critical value of 9.488, provides robust statistical evidence that constituency projects significantly improve access to educational infrastructure in rural communities of Nasarawa State. These projects have had a positive and measurable effect on improving the quality of education by addressing critical gaps in infrastructure such as classrooms, furniture, toilets, and water supply. The findings emphasise the importance of continuing these initiatives, as they play a crucial role in enhancing educational access and fostering long-term development in rural communities.

Healthcare: The findings of this study, as supported by the Chi-square test results, underscore the importance of continuing and expanding constituency projects on improving healthcare infrastructure and supplies in the communities. The significant effect of these projects on healthcare quality suggests that further investments could enhance healthcare delivery even more.

Policymakers could use these findings to advocate for increased funding and resource allocation to healthcare facilities in the communities, ensuring that they receive the necessary infrastructure and supplies to provide high-quality care. The evidence from this study provides strong support for the idea that improving healthcare facilities and services in rural communities is essential for achieving better public health outcomes and reducing healthcare disparities.

The Chi-square test result, with a calculated value of 54.84 that exceeds the critical value of 9.488, provides strong statistical evidence that constituency projects significantly improve the quality of primary healthcare services in communities in Nasarawa State. The findings highlight the positive effect of projects such as the construction of healthcare centers, provision of medical equipment and supplies, and improvements in electricity and water supply on healthcare delivery in these areas. These results emphasise the importance of continuing and expanding such projects to enhance healthcare access and quality in rural communities, ultimately contributing to better health outcomes and more equitable healthcare across the state.

Water Supply: The significant effect of the constituency projects on water infrastructure in Nasarawa State is an essential finding that highlights the effectiveness of constituency projects interventions in addressing a critical development challenge in rural communities. Access to clean water is fundamental

for improving public health, reducing waterborne diseases, and enhancing the overall standard of living in rural communities.

These findings align with the broader goal of improving basic services and infrastructure in rural communities. Prior to these projects, many rural areas in Nasarawa State faced challenges related to unreliable or inadequate water supply, which hindered the health and well-being of residents. The Chi-square test results affirm that the constituency projects have addressed this gap, leading to more consistent access to clean water.

By focusing on water infrastructure, these projects have not only contributed to the immediate needs of rural communities but also supported sustainable development goals. Access to clean water improves sanitation, reduces the spread of diseases, and boosts agricultural productivity by providing a reliable water source for farming activities. These benefits, in turn, contribute to the broader socio-economic development of rural communities.

Furthermore, these findings underscore the significance of constituency projects in advancing community development objectives. The successful implementation of water-related projects provides a model for how other infrastructure interventions such as those in healthcare, education, and electricity can also have a positive, transformative effect when effectively managed and targeted. The study's findings suggest that constituency projects, when properly executed, can play a key role in improving the quality of life for rural populations in Nasarawa State.

The Chi-square test results affirm the positive impact of constituency projects on improving access to potable water in rural communities of Nasarawa State. This finding not only demonstrates the significance of these projects but also provides a basis for further strengthening and scaling up development interventions in Nasarawa State. The study's findings support the idea that constituency projects, when well-targeted and properly implemented, can substantially improve essential services like water access, which in turn contributes to the overall socio-economic development of rural areas.

Electricity: The findings of this study, supported by the Chi-square test, underscore the importance of continued investment in electricity generation and supply projects, particularly in rural communities. Since the data indicates a clear and significant effect on the quality of life, policymakers can use this evidence to advocate for further funding and support for electricity projects.

Moreover, the results suggest that policymakers should prioritise electricity access in underserved rural areas as a key component of their development strategies. Expanding electricity supply create a ripple effect, benefiting various sectors such as education, healthcare, and local economies, thereby driving long-term sustainable development.

The Chi-square test result, with a calculated value of 1010 exceeding the critical value of 9.488, provides compelling statistical evidence that constituency projects on electricity generation and supply significantly improve the quality of life in rural communities of Nasarawa State. These projects positively affect various aspects of daily life, including education, healthcare, economic activities, and general well-being. The results suggest that the continued implementation and expansion of such projects are essential for fostering sustainable development and improving the living standards of rural communities in Nasarawa State. Therefore, there is a strong case for the continued focus on electricity infrastructure as a critical driver for sustainable development.

The results suggest that continued investment in these sectors through constituency projects is crucial for rural development. However, there is a need to ensure equity in implementation to address marginalized populations, especially women and children.

Constituency projects have had statistically significant and practical impacts on key development sectors in Nasarawa State, directly improving living standards and service delivery.

Hypothesis Four

Ho: There are no significant challenges affecting the implementation of constituency projects in Nasarawa state

H1: There are significant challenges affecting the implementation of constituency projects in Nasarawa state

Response	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Strongly Agreed	146	38%
Agreed	89	23%
Undecided	31	8%
Disagreed	70	18%
Strongly Disagreed	50	13%
Total	386	100%

Table 4.34 Testing of Hypothesis (4)

RESPONSE	FO	FE	(FO-FE) ²	(FO-FE) ² /E
SA	146	77.2	4732.64	61.13
A	89	77.2	139.24	1.8
U	31	77.2	2131.44	27.6
D	70	77.2	51.84	0.7
SD	50	77.2	739.84	9.6

$X^2 = 61.13 + 1.8 + 27.6 + 0.7 + 9.6 = 101.0$

Degrees of freedom (df): No. of categories minus 1

$df = 5 - 1 = 4$

Significance level (α): 0.05

Critical value = 9.488

Decision rule: Since Calculated Chi-square value (101.0) is greater than the critical value (9.488), we reject the null hypothesis and accept the alternative hypothesis which indicates that constituency projects implementation has some challenges in Nasarawa State. This suggests that constituency projects such as electricity, education, water and healthcare projects provided through constituency projects have a significant effect on the quality of life and well-being of the people, many households have gained access to electricity, water, healthcare etc. However, challenges of implementation exist.

Results and Findings

The rejection of the null hypothesis and acceptance of the alternative hypothesis in the Chi-square test result suggest that constituency projects despite their challenges have significant impact on sustainable development of Nasarawa State.

Discussion Of The Findings

While the positive impacts are evident, several challenges limit the effectiveness of constituency projects in Nasarawa State. These include:

- i. Lack of community involvement in project selection and execution.
- ii. Inequitable distribution of projects, leading to regional and demographic disparities.
- iii. Inadequate monitoring and evaluation, which affects accountability and sustainability.
- iv. Political influence and favoritism in project allocation, which can undermine fairness and needs-based distribution.
- v. Respondents' skepticism and mixed perceptions, especially in health and education sectors, reflect these limitations. Some community members reported uncertainty about project benefits, indicating gaps in awareness, involvement, or project relevance.

Addressing these challenges requires reforms in the governance of constituency projects. This includes enhanced community participation, independent monitoring, transparent procurement processes, and

periodic audits to improve effectiveness. Despite their potential, constituency projects face several systemic challenges that hinder equitable and effective implementation. These must be addressed to maximize developmental impact.

Overall Findings and Policy Implications

The findings from the responses indicate that majority respondents had confirmed that constituency projects had generally contributed to improved education, health, water and electricity access to the community, significant effect on quality of life and local businesses, though some respondents remain skeptical or undecided about specific impacts.

However, despite their potential, constituency projects face several systemic challenges that hinder equitable and effective implementation. These must be addressed to maximize developmental impact.

Economic Implications

The positive impact on access to electricity, water, and health facilities indicates that constituency projects can serve as catalysts for local economic activities by reducing operational costs for small businesses and improving productivity. Enhanced educational infrastructure contributes to human capital development, equipping the youth with skills needed for employment and entrepreneurship. Furthermore, when effectively implemented, these projects can contribute to poverty alleviation by creating jobs during construction and through long-term use of completed facilities (e.g., schools, clinics). While systemic challenges, such as misallocation of resources and poor project selection, suggest an urgent need for better economic planning and prioritization. Addressing these issues could lead to more cost-effective use of public funds. Without transparency and accountability, constituency projects may result in duplication, abandonment, or under-utilization, leading to significant economic losses and inefficient public spending.

Social Implications

Confirmed improvements in education, health, water, and electricity access point to the positive social outcomes of constituency projects, including better health outcomes, increased school enrollment, and improved living standards. Skepticism among some respondents highlights perceived or real inequalities in project distribution. This raises the issue of equitable access to developmental benefits, especially for marginalized communities. Institutionalizing community engagement and participatory planning in project selection and monitoring can enhance trust in public institutions and promote social cohesion. If left unreformed, constituency projects risk being perceived as patronage tools, which could erode citizen confidence in government programs and widen social inequalities.

Political Implications

The current trajectory suggests a risk of constituency projects becoming tools for political patronage rather than genuine grassroots development. This can undermine democratic accountability and breed cynicism toward political leadership. Findings indicate the necessity for institutional reforms to promote transparency, accountability, and inclusivity. Stronger legal and procedural frameworks can help depoliticize constituency projects and refocus them on community needs. Involving citizens in project planning, monitoring, and evaluation could promote democratic governance and strengthen political legitimacy at the grassroots level. Where projects are impactful, it can enhance the legitimacy of representatives; where not, it may fuel political apathy or unrest.

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